

WORKING PAPER

State of digitalization in the Southeast Asia Region – bibliometric analysis

Abstract

The digital revolution is reshaping global economies and societies, and Southeast Asia is no exception. This paper presents a bibliometric analysis of the state of digitalization in Southeast Asia, focusing on the period from 2018 to 2023. By leveraging the Scopus database, we conducted a comprehensive review of literature in the digital domain, identifying key trends, regional disparities, and thematic focuses within the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) nations. Our analysis reveals significant strides in digitalization, marked by increased scholarly attention and publication output, particularly from countries like Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand. The study also highlights a stark digital divide within the region, with countries like Laos, Cambodia, and Myanmar lagging in digital infrastructure and literacy. We analyzed 5058 articles from the last five years using a bibliometric approach to assess publication patterns, author affiliations, and emerging research themes, revealing a diversified research landscape. Significant contributions were found in areas including digital governance, economy, infrastructure, and societal impacts. The paper also discusses the role of digitalization in economic growth, social inclusion, and sustainable development within the region. Our findings underscore the importance of regional collaborations and targeted policies to bridge the digital divide. We emphasize the necessity of inclusive digital strategies that consider the unique socio-economic and cultural contexts of each ASEAN country. The study provides valuable insights for policymakers, academicians, and industry stakeholders, guiding future research agendas and digital initiatives in Southeast Asia. The bibliometric analysis not only maps the scholarly terrain but also offers actionable intelligence for decision-makers in navigating the digitalization landscape across this dynamic and diverse region.

Keywords: digitalization, digital divide, Southeast Asia, bibliometric analysis

Section snippets

1. Introduction

Digitalization refers to the integration of digital technologies into organizational and operational environments, transforming both society and business (Parviainen et al., 2017, Kovač et al., 2024). This process strengthens connectivity, communication, services, and trade, as institutions adopt internet-connected digital technologies and applications (Linkov et al., 2018). Digitalization has significant impacts on B2B exchanges, facilitating activity links, resource ties, and actor bonds (Pagani & Pardo, 2017). As a transformative process, digitalization enables businesses to address economic and environmental challenges, contributing to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (Bican & Brem, 2020). Key features of digitalization include IoT technologies, intensive data exchange, and predictive analytics, which revolutionize industrial business models and support sustainability (Parida, Sjödin & Reim, 2019). Additionally, digitalization enables the emergence of new digital products and services that emphasize flexibility, promoting innovative work practices while heightening the

importance of cybersecurity and privacy (Almeida, Duarte Santos & Augusto Monteiro, 2020).
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2. Theoretical background

2.1. *The role of digitalization in economic and social development*

Digitalization significantly impacts economic and social development by boosting productivity, creating jobs, promoting innovation, and improving business operations. It also enhances communication, services, and trade, presenting unique opportunities to improve global living standards and environmental well-being. However, policymakers must also consider potential sustainability challenges and threats, including the carbon footprint associated with digital technologies and the rise of economic disparity (Linkov et al., 2018). Digital technologies are increasingly necessary for participating in the economy and engaging in society. However, unequal access to digital resources worsens social exclusion. Big data and business analytics are important tools for creating value in societies, but their availability does not always solve persistent problems for less privileged groups. It is crucial to bridge these digital gaps for sustainable, digitalized societies. Therefore, addressing digital inequalities and ensuring fairness and inclusiveness in the digital era is important (Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 2023).

3. Methodology

3.1. *Method*

In conducting our in-depth analysis, we employed a robust bibliometric approach, leveraging the vast resources of the Scopus database. With a detailed search strategy, we focused our inquiry on the dynamic intersection of "digital*" within the expansive landscape of Southeast Asia. Our targeted query spanned across specific countries, encapsulating the diverse technological landscapes of Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Singapore, Vietnam, Cambodia, Philippines, Myanmar, Laos, Brunei, and Timor-Leste.

4. Results and discussion

The utilization of the PRISMA methodology for bibliometric analysis in the study on digitalization across Southeast Asia from 2018 to 2023 reflects a systematic and comprehensive approach to gathering, assessing, and categorizing relevant scholarly works. The specified query, strategically formulated to encompass a broad spectrum of ASEAN countries, ensures inclusivity in the scope of the study, covering Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, Singapore, Vietnam, Cambodia, Philippines, Myanmar, Laos, Brunei, and Timor-Leste. This methodological choice is pivotal in capturing the diversity of digitalization efforts and scholarly contributions within the Southeast Asian context. The emphasis on the search query, combining "digital*" and specific country names, is a nuanced approach. It not only ensures the inclusivity of studies related to digitalization but also allows for a more tailored examination of the unique initiatives and challenges faced by each Southeast Asian country in its digitalization endeavours. ...

5. Conclusions

Bibliometrics analysis serves as a powerful tool in unveiling key trends and dynamics in the realm of digitalization across Southeast Asia. The breakdown of keywords provides valuable insights into the focal points of research, illuminating the diverse aspects of digitalization that scholars in the region find relevant. This understanding aids in shaping future research agendas, allowing for targeted investigations into specific dimensions of digital transformation.

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